

PHENOLIC OXIDATION. PART II. METAL HYDRIDE REDUCTION
OF DEHYDRO-*bis*(2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHYL)-METHANE

•BY J. N. CHATTERJEA

Dehydro-*bis*(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-methane has been reduced with metal hydrides and the transformation of the products interpreted in terms of Pummerer's structure for the dehydro compound.

Oxidation of phenols has received considerable attention of chemists. In particular, it has been the subject of great significance in biogenetic processes (Erdtman, *Annalen*, 1933, 508, 283 ; Harington, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 193 ; Robinson, "The Structural Relations of Natural Products", Oxford University Press, 1955, et seq). Only recently, a new interpretation of the constitution of an oxidative dimer of *p*-cresol led to a simple two-step synthesis of usnic acid by Barton and his co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 530). In an earlier paper* (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 375) dehydro-*bis*(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-methane, an oxidation product of the phenol (III), was subjected to catalytic hydrogenation and the results assessed in terms of Pummerer's expression (I) for the compound (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 3477). In the present communication the action of specific carbonyl-reducing agents has been studied with a view to examining the stability of the dihydrofuran ring.

Both the Meerwein and lithium aluminium hydride reduction afforded only one unsaturated alcohol (II), m.p. 168-69° (designated A ; the product by Meerwein's method was always purer) *without* affecting the oxide linkage in contrast to catalytic methods. By using sodium or potassium borohydride in methanol, another isomeric unsaturated alcohol, m.p. 144° (designated B) was obtained in addition, and separated with some difficulty. These isomers are found to be chemical individuals and not polymorphs. The U.V. absorption spectra of both these compounds were very similar, both exhibiting a *maxima* at 235 m μ ; the I.R. spectrum (Experimental) showed some divergence. The 3-bromo derivative of (I) on reduction with potassium borohydride also afforded a stereoisomeric mixture from which one isomer was obtained pure. In this case also the oxide link remained intact.

The above mentioned isomers, A and B, were smoothly oxidised by manganese dioxide in chloroform to (I). The Oppenauer oxidation with benzoquinone as the hydrogen acceptor was tried on (A), and a mixture of (A) and (B) ; in both cases a quantitative yield of (I) resulted. Oxidation with either acetone or cyclohexanone was not possible; the products formed in these experiments were *bis*(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-methane (III), formed by pinacolic electron displacement (as shown), and 1:2-7:8-dibenzoxanthene (IV), obviously formed from (III). The formation of these compounds was traced as due to the action of acid on (II), the driving force being the aromatisation of the reduced ring.

This paper may be regarded as Part I of this series.

In the light of these results, the two isomeric compounds, (A) and (B), are considered to be diastereoisomeric alcohols, the formation of which incidentally confirms the asymmetric nature of (I) on account of the presence of a spiro carbon atom (Aschän, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 3389; Leuchs, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 2131; Sutter and Witzmann, *Annalen*, 1935, 519, 97). The formation of two isomers by borohydride reduction against one by lithium aluminium hydride or the Meerwein reduction cannot be reconciled with the recent generalisations of Dauben *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 2579) regarding the stereochemistry of hydride reduction. Should steric factors on account of the spiro ring play an effective part, the formation of the initial complex should depend on "steric approach control", and accordingly, the greater effective size of borohydride species should have favoured the formation of one isomer more than the other.

On reduction with lithium aluminium hydride—aluminium chloride mixture (cf. Brown, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1956, 1307), (I) gave mainly the phenol (III) by cleavage of the oxide link together with a small quantity of (A). None of the expected reduction product ($=CO \rightarrow =CH_2$) appears to have been formed.

On catalytic hydrogenation, both (A) and (B) absorbed one mole of hydrogen, giving rise to corresponding isomeric saturated alcohols, one of which (from B) was identical with that obtained by direct catalytic reduction from (I); the other (from A) slowly passed in alcoholic solution or better *via* the benzoyl derivative, into the stable isomer. The cyclohexene ring of this compound can assume puckered configuration, and it is likely that the hydroxyl group of the stable epimeride occupies the more thermodynamically stable equatorial conformation.

*E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Metal Hydride Reactions

(i). *With Lithium Aluminium Hydride: Formation of 2ⁿ-Hydroxy-1ⁿ:2ⁿ-dihydro-naphthalene(1ⁿ:5)-spiro 4:5-dihydronaphtho-(1':2'-2:3)-furan (II).*—Lithium aluminium hydride (50 mg.) was added to a stirred suspension (0.2 g.) of the dehydro compound (I) in ether (15 c.c.). All the material gradually passed into a colorless solution which was then decomposed with ice-cold 10% HCl; the ethereal layer was washed with alkali (no phenolic material) and the residue after removal of ether furnished the *alcohol* (II) which crystallised from ethanol in small prisms, m.p. 166-67°, identical with the Meerwein reduction product, mentioned below. The compound dissolved in sulphuric acid with an orange-yellow colour, exhibiting an intense green fluorescence. (Found: C, 83.7; H, 5.3. C₂₁H₁₆O₂ requires C, 84.0; H, 5.5%. *I. R. spectrum*: Bands at 2.89S, 5.93M, 6.13S, 6.92S, 7.32M, 8.04M, 9.25M, 10.14S, 10.47S, 11.28M, 21.96 M, 12.31M and 12.65 M μ .

The Meerwein reduction was done by boiling a mixture of the dehydro compound (3.0 g.), isopropyl alcohol (25 c.c.) and aluminium isopropoxide (2.0 g.) under a short still-head designed to remove acetone. In about five minutes the reduction was complete as the yellow colour of the solution completely disappeared. After removing the alcohol, the residue was acidified and the solid (3 g.) was collected and crystallised from alcohol in prismatic needles (2.6 g.), m.p. 169-70°. On working up the mother-liquor a further quantity of the material was obtained.

(ii). *With Sodium or Potassium Borohydride.*—A suspension of the dehydro compound in methanol (dry, 40 c.c.) (I, 4.1 g.) was stirred and treated with potassium or sodium borohydride (0.6 g.), added in small portions. Soon after the reduction was complete, colorless crystals (2.1 g.) of (A), m.p. 167°, began to separate. This was collected and the filtrate concentrated and precipitated with water. The resulting solid was dried and dissolved in a minimum quantity of alcohol and left overnight. The crystals deposited were a mixture of hard lumps (m.p. 167°) and fine plates (B, m.p. 144°), separable mechanically. A better separation was effected by warming the mixture carefully till the plates went just into solution, leaving the lumps and then filtering quickly. The filtrate deposited crystals of the *alcohol* (II) (B, 0.36 g.). (Found: C, 83.4; H, 5.4. C₂₁H₁₆O₂ requires C, 84.0; H, 5.5%). A further quantity was obtained with difficulty by working up the mother-liquor. The compound dissolved in sulphuric acid with an orange-yellow solution, exhibiting a strong green fluorescence. *I. R. spectrum*: Bands at 6.02 M, 6.13 M, 6.99 S, 7.33 S, 8.07 M, 8.42 M, 10.08 M, 10.56 M, 11.61 M, 11.89 M, 12.14 M and 12.55 S μ . The compound gave methane with methylmagnesium iodide.

(iii). *With Lithium Aluminium Hydride-Aluminium Chloride.*—The dehydro compound (1.0 g.) was added gradually to a stirred solution of LiAlH₄ (0.42 g.) in ether (20 c.c.) to which a solution of freshly sublimed aluminium chloride (2.2 g.) in ether (20 c.c.) had been previously added with usual precautions.

* All m.p. s. are uncorrected.

The mixture was stirred for 2 hours, decomposed with moist ether, acidified with sulphuric acid, the ethereal solution separated and washed with alkali. The alkaline layer on acidification furnished *bis*(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-methane (III) (0.8 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 201°. The neutral matter (0.095 g.) was found to contain solely the unsaturated alcohol (A), m.p. 166-67°; a meticulous search did not reveal the presence of any other compound.

Potassium Borohydride Reduction of 3''-Bromo-dehydro-bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-methane.—A suspension of the compound (0.1 g.) in methanol (2 c.c.) was stirred and potassium borohydride (0.04 g.) added. The resulting colorless solution was concentrated and precipitated with water. The alkali-insoluble, colorless material (m.p. 168-200°) was a mixture of stereoisomerides which on several crystallisations from alcohol gave one *isomer*, m.p. 200°, in pure condition. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 5.1. $C_{21}H_{15}O_2Br$ requires C, 66.5; H, 5.1%).

On oxidation with manganese dioxide in chloroform (*vide infra*), the dehydro compound, m.p. and mixed m.p. 136°, was obtained back.

Manganese Dioxide Oxidation of (II).—Both the epimeric alcohols (0.1 g.) in chloroform (5 c.c.) were oxidised by refluxing with manganese dioxide (good quality, 1.0 g.) for 5 minutes and then filtered. The yellow filtrate was concentrated and the residue in each case crystallised from acetic acid, affording (I), m.p. 170°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen.

Oppenauer Oxidation of (II).—The unsaturated alcohol (A) or a mixture of (A) and (B) (as obtained in borohydride reduction) (0.5 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (20 c.c.) and then refluxed for 5 hours after addition of pure aluminium isopropoxide (0.5 g.) and benzoquinone (pure, 2.5 g.) when a deep blue precipitate separated. The mixture was then acidified, the organic matter taken up in ether, filtered, washed several times with alkali and then the solvent removed. The residue (0.45 g.) solidified in contact with alcohol and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow plates, m.p. 170°, identical with the dehydro compound (I).

Action of Acid on (II).—The compound (A, 0.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (4 c.c.) and boiled for 5 minutes after addition of a few drops of HCl (conc.). The product was taken up in ether and extracted with alkali. The alkaline solution on acidification afforded *bis*(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-methane, m.p. 201°, from acetic acid. (Found: C, 83.7, 83.8; H, 5.5, 5.6. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{16}O_2$: C, 84.0; H, 5.5%).

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 213° (lit. m.p. 213°). The neutral ethereal solution gave a yellowish material which crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish plates, m.p. 203-204° and identified as the dibenzoxanthene (IV), m.p. 203-204°. (Found: C, 89.0; H, 4.9. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{14}O$: C, 89.4; H, 4.9%).

Catalytic Reduction of (II).—The compound (A, 0.5 g.) was hydrogenated in acetic acid (5 c.c.) with the aid of pre-reduced palladised charcoal (0.2 g., 30%). One molecular proportion of hydrogen was absorbed in 10 minutes. On working up

the *product* was obtained in prismatic needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 118°. (Found: C, 83.4; H, 5.9. $C_{21}H_{13}O_2$ requires C, 83.4; H, 5.9%). On keeping in alcoholic solution or even in the solid state, the melting point slowly rose to that of the stable epimeride, m.p. 153° (*vide infra*). The benzoyl derivative, prepared in pyridine solution, was obtained as hard prisms, m.p. 138.5°, identical with benzoyl derivative of its epimeride. (Found: C, 82.6; H, 5.4. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{22}O_3$: C, 82.7; H, 5.4%). On hydrolysis with alkali the stable epimer, mentioned above, was obtained, m.p. 153°, after several crystallisations.

The compound (B) on similar hydrogenation quickly absorbed one mole of hydrogen and the product crystallised from alcohol in colorless leaflets, m.p. 153°; the mixed m.p. with the unstable isomer (m.p. 118°) was 135°, clearing at 138° and the mixed m.p. with the catalytic hydrogenation product (m.p. 143-45°) (Chatterjea, *loc. cit.*) was 149°, clearing at 152°. (Found: C, 83.5; H, 6.0. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{13}O_2$: C, 83.4; H, 5.9%).

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PHENOLIC OXIDATION. PART III. STRUCTURE OF ABEL'S ABNORMAL OXIME

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Dischendorfer's supposed identification of an abnormal oxime, isolated by Abel from dehydro-*bis*(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-methane with 3:4-6:7-dibenzoacridone, has now been disproved by a direct synthesis of the latter. Alternative structures for the 'oxime' have been discussed.

In previous papers evidence was put forward and discussed in support of the structure (I) for dehydro-*bis*(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-methane (Chatterjea, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 275; 1958, 35, 37; cf. Pummerer and Cherbuliez, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 3477; Shearing and Similes, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1931). A second structure (II, R=H), advanced originally by Kohn and Ostersetzer (*Monatsh.*, 1918, 39, 299), was specially supported by Dischendorfer (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 774) who supposed that an 'abnormal oxime' $C_{21}H_{13}NO$ (oxime